

Do we habituate to pleasant touch? Insights from event-related brain potentials (ERPs)

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Abstract. This study explores how repetition affects responses to gentle touch, focusing on C-tactile afferents (CTs), which encode positive touch sensations. Participants (N=40) received strokes on the forearm at CT-optimal and suboptimal velocities. A marginal decline in subjective and brain responses to CT-optimal velocities suggests a possible resistance to habituation. However, further work is needed to tackle potential individual habituation trajectories.

Keywords: Affective Touch, EEG, sN400, Habituation, Cable-driven robot

1 Introduction

Gentle, dynamic touch is widely recognized for its pleasant and stress-relieving effects. However, it is unclear how responses to such touch evolve over prolonged stimulation. Research has distinguished between lower-level sensory and higher-level affective habituation. Looking at sensory processes, studies on C-tactile afferents (CTs), which encode positive value of gentle touch, suggest CT firing may resist habituation [1]. Conversely, repeated touch stimulation tends to diminish positive affective responses, as shown in participants' pleasantness ratings [2]. Here, we address this inconsistency by exploring the impact of repeated tactile stimulation on the brain's representation of CT signals by examining the sN400, a potential marker of central CT processes [3].

2 Methods

2.1 Participants

The present sample comprises 40 healthy, right-handed participants (Mean age = 23.2 years, SD = 2.9). Data collection is ongoing with a target sample size of 90 participants.

2.2 Stimuli and Procedure

Tactile stimuli were linear strokes to the left forearm delivered via a soft brush held by a cable-driven robot. Small strips of copper fabrics weaved into the brush enabled contact detection via an ESP32 microcontroller. The robot stroked along a linear trajectory

of 10 cm in a to-and-from manner with a velocity of 0.5, 3, or 18 cm/s. This allowed us to fix stroke duration to 2.5 s, which was necessary for the EEG. While the 3 cm/s velocity was CT-optimal, the others were suboptimal and thus should excite CTs to a lesser extent. Pleasantness and sN400 should hence be maximal at the 3 cm/s velocity reflected by a quadratic trend across the three velocity conditions.

The experiment comprised 333 trials (111 trials/velocity) presented in a pseudo-random order and lasted around 50 minutes. The linear stroke began once the touch effector contacted the skin. For 51.4% of the trials in both trial bins, a rating scale appeared 1 s after the stroke asking participants to rate the touch pleasantness (-100 to 100). The inter-trial interval ranged between 1 and 2 s.

2.3 EEG Data Acquisition and Analysis

The 64-channel EEG was recorded with an ANT EEGo system. EEG data was low-pass and high-pass filtered at 30 and 0.1 Hz respectively, re-referenced to average reference and epoched from -1 to 1 s time-locked to touch onset. We visually rejected non-typical artifacts and removed typical artifacts via an independent component analysis. We applied a current source density transformation and baseline-corrected the data (-0.2 to 0 s). EEG data is divided into two trial bins with trials from the first and last half of the experiment. We explored the sN400 by averaging EEG trial-level data (0.3 to 0.5 s) after touch onset for relevant somatosensory channels (Cz, C2, C4).

3 Results and Discussion

Normalized pleasantness ratings were modeled with trial bin and the common logarithm of velocity (\log_{10} velocity) as fixed effects and velocity slopes and intercepts as random effects. This revealed a significant main effect of velocity ($p < .001$) driven by the quadratic ($\beta = -17.0, p < .001$) but not the linear term ($p = 0.99$). Thus, intermediate, CT-optimal velocities were most pleasant. A marginal interaction between velocity and trial bin ($p = .065$) was pursued for each trial bin (Fig. 1A). The negative quadratic term for trial bin 1 ($\beta = -13.4, p < .001$) seems larger than that for trial bin 2 ($\beta = -10.7, p < .001$) pointing to a weak reduction in the pleasantness of CT-targeted touch. Notably, there was no decline in pleasantness for other velocities.

Normalized sN400 mean values were modeled with trial bin and \log_{10} velocity as fixed effects and the subject intercepts as random effect. The velocity effect ($p < .001$) had significant linear ($\beta = 8.03, p < .001$) and quadratic terms ($\beta = 4.59, p < .001$). sN400 amplitudes were largest for the CT-optimal velocity. The interaction between velocity and trial bin failed to reach significance ($p = .10$). Nevertheless, we explored velocity effects for each trial bin. For trial bin 1, both linear ($\beta = 6.24, p < 0.001$) and quadratic terms ($\beta = 4.58, p < .001$) were significant ($M_{0.5} = -.06, SD_{0.5} = .99$; $M_3 = -.08, SD_3 = .97$; $M_{18} = .14, SD_{18} = 1.01$). For trial bin 2, the linear term was significant ($\beta = 5.08, p < .001$), but the quadratic term merely approached significance ($\beta = 1.91, p = .05$) providing weak evidence that the sN400 declines over time in a CT-specific manner ($M_{0.5} = -.07, SD_{0.5} = .99$; $M_3 = -.03, SD_3 = 1.00$; $M_{18} = .09, SD_{18} = 1.01$).

Fig. 1. Log10 velocity plotted against (A) normalized pleasantness ratings and (B) normalized sN400 amplitudes. Grey and orange lines show the quadratic fit between velocity and normalized outcome measures separately for the first and second half of the experiment, respectively. Panel C depicts the topography of the velocity effect (3 minus 18 cm/s) by trial bin.

4 Conclusion and Work in Progress Analyses

The present data align with earlier work showing that individuals habituate to the pleasantness of CT optimal stroking. Moreover, they show parallel effects for the sN400, a putative index of CT signaling in somatosensory cortex. Notably, however, critical statistical analyses yielded only marginal effects implying relatively weak habituation of CT processes. Hence, we speculate that CT driven benefits may be fairly resistant to repeated stimulation. Yet, as the current study has not reached its target sample size, we cannot rule out that there are individual differences in the processing of CT touch [4] that are associated with different habituation trajectories. We will explore this possibility as more data becomes available.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare no competing interests that are relevant to the content of this article.

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